

in the advertisement message receiving process, the first stage is “attention”, and what the “unexpected” directly affect is the consumer attention. Lee & Mason (1999) defined the unexpected advertisement as: the unusual, untraditional, novel or distinctive advertisement message presentation [4].

The concept of unexpectedness originates from the inconsistency theory, which is derived from the schema theory. Fiske (1982) defined schema as the basic cognitive structure that people use to understand things, gain knowledge and experience, and proposed the schema-triggered affect assessment model, namely, human individuals will react according to existing experience and values [5].

Petty (1983) suggested that, when the advertisement information and schema are inconsistent, the “adjusting” process would cause the consumer to spend more time in considering and elaborating, thus making the advertisement effect stronger [6]. Sherman (1998) found that when the information processing ability is low, inconsistent information would gain more attention. Secondly, when facing inconsistent information, the time for reading and reaction of the people would be longer, nevertheless, the cognitive accuracy would be higher than consistent information [7].

This study focused on the part inconsistent with schema, namely, the effect created by visual unusualness. It used the example of print advertisement to concentrate on the discussion of the impact of the “unexpected” design appeals of the inconsistency theory on communication by empirical study.

METHOD

INDEPENDENT VARIABLE

The independent variables of this study included the types of advertisement unexpectedness and the subject background. The unexpectedness types were the presentation classification of print advertisement, and the subject background was mainly based on the professional background differences. Regarding the types of advertisement unexpectedness, according to the literature review results, were summarized as the following six types, namely “imbalance”, “juxtaposition”, “displacement”, “blending”,

“context”, “overlapping” [8-10] as illustrated ad follows:

From the perspectives of Lu’s “size imbalance” theory, and the “super zoom” and “size scaled zoom” theories of Huang and He, they are all visual unexpectedness generated by changes in object size proportion, and thus, can be categorized as the same type. In fact, “shape imbalance”, “weight imbalance” and “changes in size proportion” can all be regarded as the changes in physical properties, and thus, can be categorized as the “imbalance” type of 1).

“Permutations and combinations with specific implications” means to place two objects of different contexts into a same contextual space without changing their nature and the two interact with each other rather than being placed individually to generate unexpectedness and meanings. This is categorized as the type of 2) “juxtaposition”.

“Space displacement” and “space imbalance” are to displace the objects that should not have been possible in the space. In other words, the object should not have been placed in the space or the object that should be placed in the space has been displaced by other objects to generate visual unexpectedness. This is hence categorized as the type of 3) “displacement”.

The “surface material displacement” proposed by Ho is to displace the surface material of the original object. The “biological materialization”, “non-animal personification” and the “activation of non-living things” of the surrealistic performance distinguish the creature and non-creature; they can be conceptualized as “blending of heterogeneities”. Although “surface material displacement” is very similar to surface material transformation, it can also be regarded as the blending of materials of Object A with Object B into oneness. Hence, it can be regarded as the mutual blending of two different objects and thus can be categorized as the type of 4) “blending”.

The unexpectedness generated by “context” is not the abnormality of the object itself; rather, it refers to the inconsistency of context, behavior, status with general cognition. In other words, the context may occur in real life but it is not consistent with expected status and behavior. The inconsistency between context and cognition schema generated unexpectedness, and thus it is categorized as the type of 5) “context”.

“Overlapping image” contains more complex perspectives including visual composition, grouping theory, Gestalt principles, and ambiguous figure. It is mainly to overlap the image elements with other images by the above methods, and hence it is categorized as the type of 6) “overlap”.

The following investigation uses the six types as the presentation methods of unexpectedness to compare their level of unexpectedness, and conduct cross-analysis with communication effect.

Regarding differences in professional background, as designers must understand the cognitive differences from non-designers, and review design presentation from the viewpoint of non-designers, this paper sets the professional background as the group of designers and the group of non-designers. There were 126 subjects, including 66 non-designers (52%) and 60 designers (48%).

DEPENDENT VARIABLE

Dependent variables were categorized into two parts: 1) the assessment survey of the level of unexpectedness, 2) the review of the communication effect. Conduct cross-analysis of the two parts' survey results to review the impact of the level of unexpectedness on the communication effect. The two parts survey was elaborated as follows:

Past research proposed the dual concept of expectedness, namely the “expectedness” and “unexpectedness”. This survey planned to discuss the differences in the level of “unexpectedness” and compare the differences in the level of unexpectedness of various advertisement techniques of expression. Hence, item 1 was concerned about the level of unexpectedness, and item 2 investigated the level of unexpectedness of techniques of expression. The technique of expression differed from image as image generating unexpectedness purely by visual graphics, while techniques of expression included the comprehensive judgment of images, text, products and perception of advertisement. The two differed in level, and thus, should be discussed separately.

Next, to understand the unexpectedness types and the differences in the effect of the level of unexpectedness, this study also conducted the variable operation of the communication effect. The assessment of the advertisement effect included two

assessment indicators, namely “sales effect” and “communication effect” (Leviage & Steiner, 1961) [11]. The “communication effect” can be further discussed in the cognition dimension, emotional dimension and the image dimension. The cognition dimension included the attention, understanding, acceptance and recalling of the advertisement. The emotional dimension consisted of the advertisement attitude and brand attitude while the image dimension was the purchasing intention of the consumer (Shiu, 2002) [12]. This survey was based on the communication effect of the cognitive and emotional dimensions in terms of assessment indicators.

Most of the 18 samples of this survey were award-winning printed advertisement works. The domestic advertisements were winners of Times Advertisement Awards, Chinese-language Advertisement Awards; the foreign advertisements were winners of the globally well-known advertisement journals such as Luerzer's Archive, Ads, TV and Poster world-wide.

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

The survey was divided into two parts, namely the “level of unexpectedness assessment” and the “communication effect assessment”. The level of unexpectedness assessment consisted of two questions to discuss the unexpectedness generated by visual images and the unexpectedness generated by the techniques of expression respectively. As the term “unexpectedness” may be confusing to subjects, it was replaced by “unusualness” in the image part and “uniqueness” in terms of techniques of expression. The assessment indicators of the communication effect were attention and understanding, impression, interest, and preference. The above 7 items were measured by the Likert 5-point scale (Likert, 1932), ranging from -2 to 2, as -2 is strongly disagree, -1 is disagree, 0 is no comment, 1 is agree, and 2 is strongly agree). The descriptions are shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Part 1: the level of unexpectedness

Question item	Purpose	scale
(1) Advertisement image is special	Assess the level of unexpectedness of the image	-2...-1...0...1...2
(2) Unique technique of expression	Assess the level of unexpectedness of techniques of expression	-2...-1...0...1...2

Table 1. Part 2: communication effect

Question item	Purpose	Scale
(1) The advertisement image attracts attention	Attention assessment	-2...-1...0...1...2
(2) I can understand the advertisement	Understanding assessment	-2...-1...0...1...2
(3) Advertisement leaves a strong impression on me	Impression assessment	-2...-1...0...1...2
(4) The advertisement is interesting	Interest assessment	-2...-1...0...1...2
(5) I like the advertisement	Preference assessment	-2...-1...0...1...2

RESULTS

This study conducted comparison and analysis of the survey results. The descriptive statistics of average value and the ANOVA (analysis of variance) were conducted to understand the significant differences in various types. The Pearson correlation coefficient was applied to analyze whether the level of unexpectedness was correlated to the assessment indicators of the communication effect. Finally, t-test was applied to confirm whether non-designers and designers were different in the cognition concept of unexpectedness and whether they had different cognition regarding different types.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

From the average value of the two survey results of the level of unexpectedness and communication effect, the values of image unexpectedness and technique of expression unexpectedness were respectively 0.65 and 0.66, which were slightly different from each other. Regarding the average value of the communication effect survey results, the value of attention was 0.70, and the value of the understanding was 0.74, the value of recalling was 0.49, and the value of interest was 0.48, and the value of preference was 0.30. The score of understanding was highest (0.74), and the score of preference was lowest (0.30), as most consumers may believe they had understood the advertisement appeal, but did not easily express their fondness of the advertisement.

The indicators in the category of advertisement cognition, such as attention and impression, ranked the second, while the third in scoring as the samples were all award-winning works that can relatively more easily to satisfy the two conditions. However, indicators in the category of the advertisement attitude such as interest and preference of lowest score may involve with differences in professional background and subjectivity, and thus the scores were relatively low.

Based on the average values of all samples, the Sample 2 of the “imbalance” type (Figure 1) had the highest scores in image unexpectedness (1.29), technique of expression unexpectedness (1.17), attention (1.26), impression (0.97) and its total average was highest among all samples (0.98). Sample 8 of the “displacement” type (Figure 2) had highest score in understanding (1.36); Sample 14 of the “context” type (Figure 3), had the highest scores in interest (1.02) and preference (0.68). Sample 18 of the “overlap” type (Figure 4) had lowest scores in image unexpectedness (0.21), technique of expression unexpectedness (0.17), attention (0.09), impression (-0.09).

Figure 1. sample 2

Figure 2. sample 8

Figure 3. sample 14

Figure 4. sample 18

Regarding the level of unexpectedness and communication effect, Sample 2 scored the highest in both parts as well as in terms of attention and impression, while Sample 18 scored the lowest in both parts as well as in terms of attention and impression. This study inferred that the level of unexpectedness affected the attention and impression of the communication effect. In other words, unexpected design appeal can enhance the communication effect of attention and impression due to visual unusualness. As shown in Table 2, among all types of presentations, in terms of the level of unexpectedness of image and technique of expression, the “imbalance” category had the highest scores and the “overlap” category had the lowest score. In terms of attention, the “imbalance” category had the highest score, and the “overlap” category had the lowest score. Regarding understanding, the “displacement” category had the highest score, and the “overlap” category had the lowest score. Regarding the impression, the “imbalance” category had the highest score, and the “overlap” had the lowest score. Regarding the interest, the “juxtaposition” and “context” categories had the highest scores while the “overlap” had the lowest score. Regarding preference, the “juxtaposition” and “context” category had the highest scores and the “overlap” category had the lowest score. In brief, the “imbalance” category had the highest scores in terms of the level of unexpectedness and attention while the “overlap” category had the lowest score in various indicators among all types. As to the communication effect of

types of unexpectedness, the descending order by the assessment results of the average values of various indicators were: imbalance, juxtaposition, context, displacement, blending, and overlapping.

ANOVA

ANOVA was conducted to learn whether there were significant differences in various types to confirm the type variance. Table 3 shows the differences in the level of unexpectedness of various images, and Table 4 shows the differences in the level of unexpectedness in terms of techniques of expression.

As shown in Table 3, “imbalance” and “juxtaposition”, “blending”, “displacement”, “context”, “overlap”, were different from each other significantly (.000); “juxtaposition” and “imbalance” (.000), “displacement” (.010), “overlap” (.000) were significantly different; “displacement” and “imbalance” (.000), “juxtaposition” (.010) were significantly different; “blending” and “imbalance” (.000), “overlap” (.012) were significantly different; “context” and “imbalance” were significantly different; “overlap” was significantly different from “imbalance” (.000), “juxtaposition” (.000), “blending” (.012). As seen above, “imbalance” and “juxtaposition”, displacement”, “blending”, “context”, “overlap”, were significantly different (.000). “juxtaposition” and “imbalance” (.000), “overlap” (.000) were significantly different; “displacement” and “imbalance” (.000), “overlap” (.000) were significantly different; “blending” and “imbalance” (.000), “overlap” (.012) were significantly different; “context” and “imbalance”, “overlap” were significantly different; “overlap” were significantly different from all types. The level of unexpectedness differences of various types in terms of image and techniques of expression indicated that image-generated unexpectedness was different from unexpectedness generated by advertisement techniques of expression to a certain level. As the “imbalance” category was different from all types, it can be inferred that using the “imbalance” method can get higher effect of unexpectedness. The differences in the level of unexpectedness and communication effect of various types are shown in Table 5. As seen, “imbalance” category had the highest scores in four assessment indicators of the level of unexpectedness and communication effect including

attention, impression, interest, preference and had the lowest scores in understanding similar to the “overlap” category. Regarding the communication effect, understanding was the most fundamental assessment indicator. Although the “imbalance” category had highest scores in other assessment indicators, it had the problem of understanding. Hence, in the selection of presentation types, the “imbalance” type should strengthen understanding to become the best option of unexpected design.

The “juxtaposition” type ranking the second in score in terms of attention was discussed to understand the impression of the level of unexpectedness and communication effect. “Juxtaposition”, “imbalance” and “context” topped in terms of interest and preference, and thus “juxtaposition” was also a good option of unexpected design. In fact, the presentation of “juxtaposition” contains the concept of “analogy”, which uses well-known concepts to illustrate new ideas. By analogy, information can be more easily conveyed and understood.

Other types had different effects. For example, the “context” type ranked the third in various indicators of the communication effect. As the “context” type may occur in real life, however, its behavior and state may be illogic. Hence, it may attract consumers closer and the illogic situation may be interesting to consumers. In addition, the “displacement” type had highest score in understanding. To ensure the clear communication of advertisement message to consumers, the “displacement” is also an option

PEARSON CORRELATION COEFFICIENT

The Pearson correlation coefficient was used to analyze whether the level of unexpectedness was correlated with the assessment indicators of the communication effect. The unexpectedness part was analyzed in the respects of “image” and “technique of expression”. In addition to overall discussion, various types of presentation were compared to understand the differences in the correlation level between the level of unexpectedness and communication effect in case of various types.

As shown above, the level of unexpectedness and attention were highly correlated, slightly correlated with understanding, and moderately correlated with various other indicators. Hence, image unexpectedness moderately affected various assessment indicators.

Regarding technique of expression’s the level of unexpectedness, the correlation with impression was highest followed by interest, attention, and preference. All the above assessment indicators were highly correlated with technique of expression unexpectedness and had lowest correlation with understanding at moderate level of correlation. Hence, it can be inferred that technique of expression unexpectedness can relatively highly affect attention, impression, interest, and preference and moderately affect understanding.

T-TEST

Literature suggests that different backgrounds will form different schemas, which may affect the assessment of the level of unexpectedness. This section discusses the differences in the background of the subjects. T-test was applied to confirm whether there were any differences in cognitive concepts of unexpectedness of non-designers and designers, as well as there were any cognitive differences by type. The unexpectedness was also explored in two perspectives of image and technique of expression with survey results as follows: The unexpectedness cognition of non-designers and designers was significant (.028), namely, the two had differences in the cognition of the level of unexpectedness. From the perspective of average values, non-designers had lower cognition level of the image unexpectedness than designers, hence it is confirmed: when designing advertisement, designers have to understand the cognitive differences with non-designers and review the design performance from the perspective of non-designers. Regarding the expression types, only “imbalance” category’s unexpectedness cognition had significant differences (.021), In addition to “imbalance”, non-designers and designers had no cognitive differences regarding the level of unexpectedness in the respect of other types.

Table 2. Unexpectedness level and communication effect of types of unexpectedness

Type	Image unexpectedness	Technique of expression unexpectedness	Attention	Understanding	Impression	Interest	Preference	overall assessment
Imbalance	1.07	1.02	1.09	0.47	0.79	0.64	0.43	0.79
Juxtaposition	0.72	0.70	0.94	1.02	0.61	0.67	0.40	0.72
Displacement	0.50	0.66	0.49	1.04	0.52	0.53	0.42	0.59
Blending	0.63	0.60	0.51	0.66	0.33	0.34	0.13	0.46
Overlap	0.41	0.34	0.40	0.43	0.10	0.01	-0.02	0.24
Context	0.60	0.65	0.76	0.78	0.57	0.67	0.42	0.64

Table 3 Image the level of unexpectedness differences

Type	Average	Significance
Imbalance-juxtaposition	0.344*	.000
Imbalance-displacement	0.566*	.000
Imbalance-blending	0.434*	.000
Imbalance-context	0.471*	.000
Imbalance-overlap	0.653*	.000
Juxtaposition-displacement	0.222*	.010
Juxtaposition-blending	0.090	.750
Juxtaposition-context	0.127	.389
Juxtaposition-overlap	0.310*	.000
Displacement-blending	-0.132	.341
Displacement-context	-0.095	.702
Displacement-overlap	0.087	.773
Blending-context	0.037	.993
Blending-overlap	0.220*	.012
Context-overlap	0.183	.064

Table 4 The level of unexpectedness differences by technique of expression

Type	Average	Significance
Imbalance-juxtaposition	0.320*	.000
Imbalance-displacement	0.365*	.000
Imbalance-blending	0.418*	.000
Imbalance-context	0.376*	.000
Imbalance-overlap	0.680*	.000
Juxtaposition-displacement	0.045	.992
Juxtaposition-blending	0.098	.799
Juxtaposition-context	0.056	.980
Juxtaposition-overlap	0.360*	.000
Displacement-blending	0.053	.984
Displacement-context	0.011	1.000
Displacement-overlap	0.315*	.000
Blending-context	-0.042	.994
Blending-overlap	0.262*	.005
Context-overlap	0.304*	.000

Table 5 Differences in types of unexpectedness levels and communication effect

Unexpectedness	Image	Imbalance > juxtaposition > blending > context > displacement > overlap
	Technique of expression	Imbalance > juxtaposition, blending, context, displacement > overlap
Communication effect	Attention	Imbalance > juxtaposition > context > blending, displacement, overlap
	Understanding	Displacement. > juxtaposition > context > blending > imbalance, overlap
	Impression	Imbalance > juxtaposition, context > displacement > blending > overlap
	Interest	Imbalance, juxtaposition, context > displacement > blending > overlap
	Preference	Imbalance, juxtaposition, context, displacement > blending, overlap

Table 6. Correlation between unexpectedness and communication effect

	All		Imbalance		Juxtaposition	
	Image	Technique	Image	Technique	Image	Technique
Attention	.718	.775	.661	.703	.653	.680
Understanding	.452	.432	.263	.381	.420	.451
Impression	.634	.792	.551	.689	.604	.741
Interest	.635	.769	.514	.590	.490	.685
Preference	.522	.707	.359	.498	.352	.525

	Displacement		Blending		Context		Overlap	
	Image	Technique	Image	Technique	Image	Technique	Image	Technique
Attention	.496	.643	.649	.656	.599	.667	.678	.729
Understanding	.321	.481	.504	.452	.286	.277	.391	.420
Impression	.442	.713	.609	.647	.546	.701	.518	.724
Interest	.416	.731	.571	.664	.592	.706	.531	.653
Preference	.403	.677	.506	.569	.508	.683	.527	.663

CONCLUSIONS

This study explored the effect of visual unusualness and discussed the impact of unexpected” design appeal of the inconsistency theory on communication. A survey on the level of unexpectedness assessment survey was conducted, and the communication effect evaluation survey was conducted to verify the relationship between unexpectedness and attention. This study also discussed the impact of unexpected appeal on other effects including understanding, impression, interest, preferences. The conclusions are illustrated as follows:

- Expression types and the level of unexpectedness
The differences of level of unexpectedness of various techniques of expression were: “imbalance” type’s the level of unexpectedness was highest followed by “juxtaposition”, “displacement”, “blending”, “context” at moderate level of unexpectedness and the “overlap” type at the lowest. Regardless of image unexpectedness or technique of expression unexpectedness, “imbalance” type’s unexpected operation will generate relatively higher unexpectedness.
- Unexpected and communication effect
Image unexpectedness and various communication effect indicators including attention, understanding, impression, interest, and preference were moderately correlated. Image unexpectedness and various communication effects were mutually influential. Attention had the highest correlation with image unexpectedness, namely, the higher level of

unexpectedness is, and the higher advertisement attention will be, which verifies the proposal of past research: image unexpectedness operations can enhance the advertisement attention.

Technique of expression unexpectedness and assessment indicators including attention, impression, interest, preference were highly correlated while operations of technique of expression unexpectedness affect the above indicators considerably. It is moderately correlated with understanding. Impression is the indicator with highest correlation with the unexpectedness of technique of expression. A higher level of unexpectedness of technique of expression indicates stronger advertisement impression.

The comparison of the unexpectedness of image and technique of expression indicated that technique of expression unexpected operations also include product, text, understanding and other factors, and thus, has higher level of impact on the communication effect. Hence, to improve the advertisement communication effect, in addition to image unexpectedness, other

Table 7. T-test of image unexpectedness level by consumers

		Average	t value	P value
All	Non-designers	0.57*	2.220	.028
	Designers	0.75*		
Imbalance	Non-designers	0.94*	2.342	.021
	Designers	1.20*		
Juxtaposition	Non-designers	0.63	1.722	.088
	Designers	0.82		
Displacement	Non-designers	0.39	1.959	.052
	Designers	0.62		
Blending	Non-designers	0.53	1.889	.061
	Designers	0.74		
Overlap	Non-designers	0.36	0.885	.378
	Designers	0.47		
Context	Non-designers	0.54	1.041	.300
	Designers	0.66		

factors should be taken into consideration to get the more comprehensive communication effect.

- Communication effect of various expression types
“Imbalance” type has relatively good performance in assessment indicators such as unexpectedness, attention, impression, interest, preference but

relatively poor performance in understanding. Hence, in the selection of expression type, the “imbalance” operation takes the designers more time to enhance advertisement understanding to get better communication effect.

Non-designers and designers had differences in cognition of the level of unexpectedness of images. Non-designers’ unexpectedness cognition level will be lower than that of the designers. Hence, when designing advertisement, designers should understand the differences in cognition with non-designers, and review design performance from the perspective of non-designers.

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